

LEGAL OBLIGATIONS AS AN ELEMENT OF THE JURIDICAL STATUS OF THE PERSON

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The article analyzes various approaches to the understanding of legal duties as an essential element of the legal status of an individual. The indissoluble connection and the dialectical unity of rights and obligations and their key importance in determining the legal status of a person and a citizen in society and the state are noted. Based on the study of various scientific positions, authors suggest the definition of legal obligations as an element of the legal status of an individual.

Keywords: *the legal status of a person; legal obligations; constitutional obligations; unity of rights and obligations.*

OBLIGAȚIA CA ELEMENT AL STATUTULUI JURIDIC AL PERSOANEI

Articolul analizează diferite abordări ale înțelegerii obligației ca element esențial al statutului juridic al unei persoane. Se remarcă legătura indisolubilă și unitatea dialectică a drepturilor și obligațiilor și importanța lor fundamentală în determinarea statutului juridic al unei persoane și al unui cetățean în societate și în stat. Pe baza studiului diferitelor poziții științifice, autorii propun definirea obligațiilor legale ca element al statutului juridic al unei persoane.

Cuvinte-cheie: *statutul juridic al persoanei; obligații legale; obligații constituționale; unitate a drepturilor și obligațiilor.*

Legal obligations are considered to be the most important element of the legal status of the individual, the inclusion of which in this legal concept does not cause doubts and disputes among scientists. If human rights traditionally have been given enough attention, a lot of scientific research has been devoted to them, then the nature and importance of legal obligations in science is paid with insufficient attention; they invariably remain “in the shadow”, in the background. At the same time, the legal duties of the individual are the same significant element of the legal regulation of relations between a person, society, state, as well as rights and freedoms.

Modern theoretical and legal science considers legal obligations as the most important means of legal regulation, a way to strengthen constitutionality, law and order. There is an awareness that the legal obligations in unity with the rights and freedoms of the individual constitute the universal principle of democratic organization of public life, the functioning of the rule of law, the implementation of the principle of justice and equality before the law.

Special literature gives many definitions of legal obligations, the authors of which focus on various aspects of the phenomenon under consideration. Here are some of them. The individual's legal duties are the established and state-guaranteed requirements for human behavior, the official measure of proper behavior [1, p. 474]. Practically in the same aspect he determined the legal obligation and S.F. Kechekian: “a legal obligation is a requirement stipulated in the norms of law and secured by state coercion, the need for certain behavior” [2, p. 60]. S.N. Bratus define it as

a duty, the need for behavior on the part of the obliged person: there is no choice but to exercise this behavior [3, p. 11]. N.V. Vitruk gives a detailed definition of a legal obligation: “this is a socially determined and guaranteed necessary opportunity in the behavior of an individual, the boundaries of which are determined by the norms of objective law (constitution, laws) in order to use certain goods and values to satisfy both their own and public, corporate other needs and interests based on their unity and combination” [4, p. 254].

As we can see, representatives of the Russian legal science, offering various formulations of the concept of legal duties, are unanimous in the opinion that duties are a certain measure of proper and necessary behavior established and protected by the state.

Moldovan lawyers, exploring the issues of the concept and essence of legal duties, identify two characteristic features of duties:

1. they are necessary and vital for the existence of the state, ensuring legal, social and political order;
2. they are fixed in the Constitution of the state as an act of higher legal force [5, p. 294].

In the Romanian legal doctrine, researchers note the following features of legal duties:

- duties act as a measure of proper and necessary, and not possible behavior of a person, unlike rights;
- they entail the fulfillment of requirements that are determined by the objectives and goals of the society;
- the main duties are directly enshrined in the Constitution, therefore, they enshrine such a measure of behavior, to which society attaches special importance;

- legal obligations are ensured by persuasion or, if necessary, by coercive force of the state [6, p. 165].

Legal duties are a prerequisite for the optimal interaction of the state, law and individuals, without which a balanced legal system, effective legal regulation, ensuring the rights and freedoms of citizens are impossible.

Duty – a way to ensure rights, the condition of their reality and effectiveness. These categories can actually act only in one bundle, and not separately. This is their unity. As is known, a legal obligation always corresponds to a certain subjective right. The connection and unity of rights and obligations are vividly and aptly expressed by well-known lawyers: a subjective right without a corresponding duty “becomes a legal void, because it cannot be guaranteed by the coercive power of the state” (S.S. Alekseev); “the right of the individual, not secured by the duty opposing him, is transformed from a specific law’s precise measure of possession of a social blessing into a pious wish, into an empty phrase” (I.E. Farber); “there are no rights without obligations, no obligations without rights” (K. Marx). On the unity and interrelation of the rights and obligations of I.A. Ilyin wrote the following: “People who do not know their duties are not able to observe them either; people who do not know their authority arbitrarily exceed them or are cowardly inferior to power; prove doomed to legal insanity” [7, p. 24].

Montesquieu considered duties as the highest virtue inherent in democracy. “If I could do this,” he wrote, “so that people would get new reasons to love their duties, their homeland and their laws, so that they would feel happier in any country ... I would consider myself the happiest of mortals” [8, p. 160].

Hegel, supporting the idea of the inseparable connection between rights and obligations, emphasized that they “are connected in the same respect, are correlative, first of all, in the sense that some right on my part corresponds to another in some duty. If only for one side all rights, then the whole would be disintegrated. Responsibilities towards others are first and foremost legal obligations that need to be combined with the desire to act fairly” [9, p. 294].

For the consolidation and sustainable development of the legal status of the individual, it is important to find a reasonable balance between rights and duties, which in turn would reflect a compromise between the interests of the state, society and citizen. The principle of unity of rights and obligations also follows from the recognition of the mutual responsibility of the state and the individual. This directly affects the strength and inviolability of the legal status of the individual.

The unity and interrelation of rights and obligations have not only theoretical expression, but also normative consolidation. For example, the Italian Constitution states: “The Republic recognizes, guarantees inalienable human rights and requires the fulfillment of inalienable duties arising from political, economic and social solidarity.” The Constitution of Japan states that “rights are inviolable and eternal. The people must refrain from any abuse of freedoms and rights, bear responsibilities and permanent responsibility for using them in the interests of public welfare” [10]. This means that the principle of the unity of rights and obligations also has a moral content.

The principle of unity of rights and obligations was developed in international acts. In particular, in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948, which states that “everyone has responsibilities to a society in which the free and full development of his personality is possible. In exercising his rights and freedoms, everyone should be subject only to such restrictions as established by law solely for the purpose of ensuring due recognition and respect for the rights and freedoms of others and satisfying the just demands of morality, public order and general welfare in a democratic society” (art.29). The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights stipulates that “an individual has duties towards other people and the collective to which he belongs.”

The principle of unity of rights and obligations, of course, strengthens the legal status of the individual. It is very important when the performance of duties by members of society is based not on fear of possible coercion in the event of non-compliance, but on the strength of belief in justice and social expediency of duties, on the basis of awareness of their objective necessity. Reasonable combination, interaction are the most important prerequisite for the improvement and development of the legal status of the individual.

As noted earlier, the basic, fundamental legal obligations are enshrined in the Constitution – the supreme law of the state. Most often, the duties, along with the rights and freedoms, are placed in a separate section or part of the Constitution, forming in the aggregate the constitutional and legal status of the individual. Thus, the Constitution of the Republic of Moldova in Chapter III of Section II establishes the following duties: the exercise of its constitutional rights and freedoms in good faith, without violating the rights and freedoms of others (art. 55); loyalty to the country (art. 56); homeland defense (art. 57); participation in financial expenses (art. 58); environmental protection and monuments (art. 59). As you can see, the Constitution of Moldova enshrines a smaller amount of constitutional obligations

than rights (fundamental rights and freedoms are enshrined in Articles 24-54 of the Constitution). The absence of a wide range of constitutional duties is caused by the tradition to enshrine in constitutions, first of all, rights and freedoms and by focusing on the most socially significant duties of a person and citizen.

The constitutional (main) duties of an individual are only a small part of the duties of a member of society, but some are extremely significant. B.S. Ebzeev writes that the Constitution establishes the most significant options or types of social behavior and social behavior desirable for its members as “the main duties” [11, p. 15].

The peculiarity of the main (constitutional) duties is that they have a universal character; do not depend on the specific legal status of the person; secured at a higher, constitutional level; ensure the normal functioning of the state itself, and thus the functioning of society [12, p. 242].

Constitutional law proposes various scientific approaches to the understanding of constitutional duties. Of course, any author’s definition is not universal and definitive. As rightly noted by A.P. Panov, “an attempt to give a truly universal definition of the concept of” constitutional duty “will irreversibly lead to the impoverishment of its content, the loss of some essential features” [13].

Quite often, the definition of constitutional duties is given through the category of “requirements”: these are the state-imperious requirements for an individual regarding the type and measure of its proper behavior established by the Constitution in accordance with the development needs of society and the state [14, p. 148]; these are constitutionally secured and protected by legal responsibility requirements that are imposed on a person and a citizen and are related to the need for his participation in ensuring the interests of society, the state, and other citizens [15]; these are constitutionally fixed and state-protected requirements for every person and citizen [16, p. 102]; these are enshrined in the Constitution in the interests of the state, society, citizens universal general legal requirements for the necessary behavior of all members of society and certain groups of citizens [17, p. 13].

Some scholars reveal the concept of “constitutional obligations” through the category of “necessity.” L.D. Voevodin argues that the constitutional (main) duty is “a state established in the interests of all members of society and a necessity enshrined in its Constitution that prescribes to each citizen a certain kind and measure of behavior and responsibility for improper performance” [18, p. 141]. According to the constitutional duty, A.P. Panov understands “a state-appropriate need dictated by the realities

of social development, the proper behavior of an individual, enshrined at a constitutional level in order to implement the ideals of a democratic society and legal state more fully and consistently” [19, p. 6].

S.A. Avakyan connects constitutional duties with individual freedom and notes that “individual freedom is not only the freedom to exercise one’s rights, but also the freedom of self-restraint in favor of those communities in which a person resides. Ideally, his duties in society and the state. But in the interests of the equal position of all in the performance of duties, they are enshrined in law, and the most important of them are raised to the level of constitutional duties” [20, p. 503].

The value of constitutional duties is as follows:

1) constitutional obligations are fundamental for determining the balance of interests of a person, society, state;

2) constitutional obligations occupy a dominant position in the entire system of legal obligations and have a decisive influence on this system, acting as the basis for determining the list and content of obligations fixed by sectoral legislation;

3) the constitutional duties of the individual serve as a condition for the existence of the state, the performance of its functions, a way to protect and preserve the values of society;

4) constitutional obligations act as a guarantee for other members of society to exercise their rights and freedoms;

5) the implementation of constitutional duties provides the possibility of normal coexistence of individuals in society.

Summarizing the above and other scientific opinions and approaches to understanding legal duties, we can formulate the following definition: legal duties are the basic requirements fixed in the Constitution for the necessary and proper behavior of all members of society and individual groups of citizens, establishing the measure and type of such behavior in the interests of citizens, society and the state.

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